
Uncontrolled HIV- Weakens the Immune System, Spreads AIDS Widely, Which Possibly Engulf the World Within A Limited Period

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Abstract:

HIV is emerging as a devastating disease in the world; if it continues to grow at this rate, it will be impossible to see a non-infected person in future. Its spread is due to a lack of knowledge as well as poor attention towards this disease. To create awareness, the World Health Organization formulated various strategies to control the infection. Recently, various experiences show that the "HAART" regimen is more helpful for the individual to control HIV infection if detected earlier. As well as they can lead a normal life, however need to take medicine long period of time to control and maintain the viral load level. People with HIV who are on ART and have an undetectable viral load will not pass HIV to their sexual partners. Early access to ART and support to stay on treatment is therefore essential not only to improve the health of people living with HIV but also to prevent HIV transmission.

Keywords-

HIV -Human immunodeficiency virus, AIDS-Acquired immunodeficiency, HAART-Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy, SIV-simian immunodeficiency virus.
